

REGIONAL INVESTMENT PROJECTS IMPLEMENTED IN NAVOY REGION.

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Abstract: Navoi region is an industrialized area. The mining, chemical, building materials and textile industries are the drivers of the region's economy. More than 65 trillion soums of industrial products are produced here. This article provides information on regional investment projects implemented in 2022 in Navoi region, including Khatirchi district.

Key words: investment, production, projects, foreign investments, export of products.

Navoi region is a region within the Republic of Uzbekistan. It was established on April 20, 1982 from the territories of Bukhara and partially Samarkand regions. It was abolished as an administrative unit in 1988 and was revived in early 1992. The area is 111.0 thousand km². Navoi region is located in the central part of the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan and occupies a large part of the Kyzylkum desert. Its area is equal to 110.8 thousand km², in this respect it is the largest region. Navoi region is bordered by Karakalpakstan in the west, Kazakhstan in the north, Jizzakh in the east, and Kashkadarya and Bukhara regions in the south.

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Navoi region is rich in significant natural resources, including natural gas, oil, nonferrous metals, and raw materials for construction. The main structure of the region's economy consists of large mining, metallurgical and chemical complexes. Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Combine (NKMK), located in Navoi region, is one of the purest gold producers in the world. A cement factory, a chemical complex and a number of large industrial plants are also operating in the region. The main products of agriculture are cotton and Karakol sheep products. If the necessary sources of irrigation are found and established, then 90% of the land in the region will have productive potential.

10.6 trillion in Navoi region in January-December 2022. Soums of foreign investment and loans were absorbed into the fixed capital. 889.0 billion of them. foreign loans under the

guarantee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 9.7 trillion soums. direct foreign investments and unsecured foreign loans, 43.3 billion soums. soums made other foreign investments.

About regional investment projects implemented in the district in 2022

Projects in the approved program:

The total amount realized in Khatirchi district in 2022

As a result of launching 60 projects worth 154 billion 375 million soums, 395 new jobs were created.

Including in the cross-section of directions:

- Industry - 14, 43.4 billion soums, 148 jobs
- Service - 32, 54.5 billion soums, 127 jobs
- Agriculture - 14, 56.4 billion soums, 120 jobs

Production of new types of products:

In 2022, the production of 2 types of new products was launched in Khatirchi district

"BEAUTIFUL SAMARKAND" LLC has installed equipment capable of producing 500 tons of asphalt per day and started working.

"KAFOLAT SANTECHNIKA SERVIS" JSC installed a production line for household appliances (including gas stove, air conditioner, iron, monitor, etc.) and created 30 new jobs.

About the export indicators of Khatirchi district. In 2022, 16 enterprises in the district exported products worth 45.3 million dollars (42 million dollars - industrial products, 3.3 million dollars - fruits and vegetables) to Asian and European countries. In the export of industrial products, kalava yarn, silk and wheat flour had the main share, while in the agricultural products, raisins and legumes, dried fruits and tomatoes were the main part of the export.

Absorption of foreign investments

12.1 mln by the end of the year within the framework of 3 projects and 12 additional projects based on the Investment Program in 2022. Foreign investments in dollars have been absorbed.

According to the official release, 576 projects are planned to be implemented in Navoi region this year. Their total value is 18.6 trillion soums. In terms of sectors, 200 of the projects are industrial, 179 are in the service sector, and 197 are in the agricultural sector. As a result of this, the production capacity of about 18 trillion soums will be created and 16 thousand jobs will be created. It is planned to prepare 123 million dollars worth of import substitution products and provide 125 million dollars worth of exports.

20 projects have been created in the chemical industry, 9 of them will be commissioned this year. As a result, new products in high demand will be developed and more than 430 people will be employed.

Projects in the textile industry are also promising. In particular, this year, 28 enterprises will be established in all cities and districts, and about 5,800 jobs will be created.

Most of the exported products are cotton fiber, ammonium nitrate, chemical fiber, sulfate, ammonium, orthoaminophenol. Consumer goods, calcium carbide, caustic soda, thiomochovina, sewing equipment, medical equipment, trucks and light cars, buses and their spare parts, farm equipment are brought from abroad. The main branches of agriculture are cotton growing, grain growing, as well as horticulture, viticulture, vegetable growing, cocoon growing, and livestock production. Animal husbandry is multifaceted. More than 228,000 pieces of black leather are produced (2003). Navoi region ranks first in the country in the production of black leather. It is also famous for the production of fabrics, especially high-

quality velvet. The area of land used for agriculture is 9266.2 thousand ha, the area of arable land is 111.1 thousand ha, pastures are 9137.5 thousand ha (2003). The total cultivated area is 112,600 ha, including 39,400 ha of cotton, 42,000 ha of grain crops, and 1,400 ha of potatoes, vegetables and sugarcane crops. In order to improve land reclamation, 2.6 thousand km of collector-drainage networks and 138 drainage wells were built. In the Navoi region, agricultural fields are supplied with water through the Navoi, Ortakhol, Amu, Sumbul, Maina branches of the Amu-Bukhara machine canal, as well as the Toss, Shavot, Chovli, Right and Left Bank, Navkar, Konimekh canals that receive water from the Zarafshan River. There are 32 large water pumping stations. There are 75 companies and 4,000 farms in Navoi region.

There are 200,000 cattle (including 96,400 cows), 1,458,000 sheep and goats, and 723,000 poultry in regional private and collective farms (2003).

Summary. Navoi region is one of the youngest regions in Uzbekistan. Its administrative center, the city of Navoi, was established in 1958. This place for the construction of the city was not chosen by chance. The mining and metallurgical industry is rapidly developing here. In this region, especially in the Khatirch district of the region, significant investments were made last year, many projects were implemented. We invite all tourists and innovators to Khatirchi district of Navoi region...

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 2, 2008 No. PF-4059 "On the establishment of a free industrial and economic zone in Navoi region".
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 10, 2012 No. PF-4434 "On additional measures to encourage foreign direct investment".
3. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 13, 2012
4. Decree No. PF-4436 on the establishment of the "Angren" special industrial zone.

